

Electrochemical Reductions. Cyclic Voltammetry and Chronopotentiometry of some Substituted Phenacyl Bromides

A. SIVARAMI REDDY and S. JAYARAMA REDDY*

Electrochemical Laboratories, Sri Venkateswara University, Tirupati-517 502

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The electrochemical reductions of *p*-bromo-, *p*-chloro- and *p*-nitro-phenacyl bromides have been carried out using the techniques of cyclic voltammetry and chronopotentiometry at hanging mercury drop electrode. Comparative account of their behaviour in different supporting electrolytes studied is presented. Reduction mechanism is discussed. The kinetic parameters such as forward rate constants and diffusion coefficients evaluated for the reduction process are reported.

THE electrochemical reduction of compounds containing carbon-halogen bond has been studied systematically¹⁻³ and it has been reviewed by many others⁴⁻⁷. In general, the fission of carbon-halogen bond is a one-step two-electron, diffusion-controlled process, probably through a free radical and/or carbanion stage. The ease of reductive dehalogenation of simple monohaloalkylhalides is in the order, R-I > R-Br > R-Cl and tertiary R-X > secondary R-X > primary R-X. In polyhalomethyl groups, such as X₃C or X₂CR, the fission of carbon-halogen bond takes place in a stepwise manner. The first C-X bond fission will be easier than the remaining C-X bonds, with C-F₃ being an exception. Carbon-halogen bond fission in aromatic and vinyl halides is difficult when compared to that of alkyl halides. In α -halo ketones, the reduction of carbon-halogen bond takes place at more positive potentials than in analogous normal halides. A considerable number of investigations have been reported on the electrochemical reductions of α -halo ketones⁸⁻¹⁰. The ease of reduction of carbon-halogen bond in α -halo ketones has been attributed to the presence of carbonyl group adjacent to the carbon bearing halogen atom. The polarographic studies of α -bromo ketones showed that the fission of carbon-bromine bond is complicated by the appearance of maxima, hydrolysis *etc.*¹¹ in aqueous buffer solutions. In the present study, the electrochemical reduction of carbon-bromine bond in three substituted phenacyl bromides, *p*-bromophenacyl bromide, *p*-chlorophenacyl bromide and *p*-nitrophenacyl bromide has been investigated using cyclic voltammetric and chronopotentiometric techniques in order to get more insight into the reduction mechanism. Acetate buffer of pH 5.5 and 6.5, ammonium chloride-ammonia buffer of pH 8.2, 0.1 M lithium perchlorate and 0.1 M tetraethylammonium bromide (TEAB) all prepared in

ethanol-water (1 : 1) mixtures are used as supporting electrolytes.

Theory :

The theoretical principles of cyclic voltammetry and chronopotentiometry have been discussed in detail¹²⁻¹⁴. Reddy *et al.*¹⁵⁻¹⁸ have used cyclic voltammetry and chronoamperometry extensively to study the electrochemical oxidations of several organic compounds. The diffusion coefficients of the species under consideration are evaluated from the equation,

$$i_p = 3.01 \times 10^5 n (\alpha n_s)^{1/2} A D^{1/2} C v^{1/2} \quad (1)$$

where, i_p = peak current (μA), n = number of electrons involved in the electrode reaction, A = area of the electrode (cm^2), D = diffusion coefficient ($cm^2 s^{-1}$), C = concentration of the electrode species ($mmol dm^{-3}$), α = transfer coefficient, n_p = number of electrons in rate determining step, and v = rate of potential change ($V s^{-1}$).

In the present study, the reduction process being found irreversible, the forward rate constant ($k_{f,h}$) values are evaluated from the relation¹⁹,

$$E_p = -1.14 \frac{RT}{\alpha n_s F} + \frac{RT}{\alpha n_s F} \ln \frac{(k_{f,h}^0)}{D^{1/2}} - \frac{RT}{2\alpha n_s F} \ln (\alpha n_s v) \quad (2)$$

The relationship between the quantitative aspects of chronopotentiometry has been derived,

$$\tau^{1/2} = \frac{\pi^{1/2} n F D^{1/2} C}{2i} \quad (3)$$

which is known as the Sand equation²⁰. In the above equation, C is the bulk concentration of the reactant ($mol cm^{-3}$), τ is the transition time, and i is the constant current density applied. The other terms have their usual significance. The constancy of the product ($i\tau^{1/2}$) is tested to know about any complications in the electrode reaction from coupled

homogeneous chemical reactions, adsorption *etc.* The diffusion coefficient of the species is also evaluated from the above relation.

When the electron transfer process is irreversible under linear diffusion conditions, for a cathodic process, the following equation is applicable^{2,2},

$$E_t = \frac{RT}{\alpha n_a F} \ln \frac{nFC^0 k_{f,h}^0}{i_0} + \frac{RT}{\alpha n_a F} \ln [1 - (t/\tau)^{1/2}] \quad (4)$$

where, E_t is the electrode potential, and i_0 is the constant current density applied. The αn_a values for the reduction process are evaluated from the plots of E vs $\log [1 - (t/\tau)^{1/2}]$, whose reciprocal slope is equal to $2.3 RT/(\alpha n_a F)$. From the above plots the potential at zero time, $E_{t=0}$ is obtained,

$$E_{t=0} = \frac{RT}{\alpha n_a F} \ln \frac{nFC^0 k_{f,h}^0}{i_0} \quad (5)$$

Using equation (5), the forward rate constants, $k_{f,h}^0$ are also evaluated for the reduction process under consideration.

Experimental

Electroscan 30 (Beckman) was used to record the cyclic voltammograms and chronopotentiograms. A three compartment cell was used for this work (Fig. 1). The cell containing three compartments was made by fusing G_1 -frits in the two side-arms. A paste of agar agar in saturated KCl solution was poured into the side-arms. The auxiliary platinum electrode and reference SCE

Fig. 1. Three compartment cell: (A) side-arm for auxiliary electrode, (B) working electrode compartment, and (C) side-arm for reference electrode.

were connected with the side-arms filled with KCl agar bridge. The sample solution was poured into the middle compartment and deoxygenated with purified nitrogen gas before experiment. The hanging mercury drop of area 0.0437 cm^2 was used as the working electrode throughout the studies.

For the evaluation of electrochemical area of the working electrode, chronoamperometry data of standard cadmium reduction has been employed.

All the three compounds *p*-bromo-, *p*-chloro- and *p*-nitro-phenacyl bromides were prepared by direct bromination of the corresponding acetophenones^{23,24}. *p*-Bromo- and *p*-chloro-phenacyl bromides obtained were recrystallised several times from rectified spirit, while for *p*-nitrophenacyl bromide, benzene-petroleum ether was used. The purity of the sample was tested in each case by melting through its m.p., ir spectra, and molecular weights by vapour pressure osmometer. Absolute ethanol was used for preparing the stock solutions before the experiment. The test solutions were prepared by diluting 0.01 M stock solution (1 ml) with the supporting electrolyte (A.R. grade) in 10 ml volumetric flask, which was then transferred into the middle compartment of the three-compartment cell. A Elico digital pH meter was used for pH measurements, and nitrogen gas after passing through potassium hydroxide, concentrated sulphuric acid and silica gel traps was bubbled through the test solution for about 10–15 min to remove dissolved oxygen, and later allowed to pass over the surface of the solution to maintain inert atmosphere. The experiments were carried out at $25 \pm 1^\circ$. Blank voltammograms were recorded prior to the addition of electroactive species, and the net current was calculated after applying suitable correction in all the experiments.

Results and Discussion

Characterisation of peaks: In *p*-chloro-, *p*-bromo- and *p*-nitro-phenacyl bromides, the reduction peak at more positive potentials is found to be due to the reduction of carbon-bromine bond as proved by the product analysis. The second peak appearing in the case of *p*-chloro- and *p*-bromo-phenacyl bromides is due to the reduction of corresponding ketone that is formed in the first step, which was conformed from the coincidence of the peak potential for the corresponding acetophenone. In *p*-nitrophenacyl bromide, two peaks appeared in addition to the reduction peak of carbon-bromine bond. The second and third peaks of *p*-nitrophenacyl bromide are found to be due to the reduction of nitro and keto groups, respectively, which was confirmed from the coincidence of peak potentials with that of *p*-nitroacetophenone (Fig. 2). In all the media studied the shift of peak potential towards negative side with increasing pH is observed. A comparison of E_p values at sweep rate $0.04 - 0.05 \text{ Vs}^{-1}$ is presented in Table 1.

For all the three compounds under consideration in all the media studied, no peak is observed in the reverse scan in cyclic voltammetry. A shift of E_p with scan rate is also observed which indicates that the reduction process of carbon-bromine bond is irreversible. The nature of the reverse chronopotentiograms also supports the hypothesis of irreversibility of the reduction process. A typical

Fig. 2. Cyclic voltammograms for the comparison of nitro and keto group reduction peak potentials in acetate buffer of pH 5.5 in ethanol-water (1:1): (A) *p*-nitroacetophenone, and (B) *p*-nitrophenacyl bromide; scan rate = 0.04 Vs⁻¹, concn. = 1 mM.

Fig. 3. Typical chronopotentiogram for *p*-bromophenacyl bromide; background, acetate buffer of pH 6.5 in ethanol-water (1:1).

TABLE 1—COMPARISON OF E_p VALUES FOR SUBSTITUTED PHENACYL BROMIDES

Sweep rate = 0.04 - 0.05 Vs⁻¹

Sl. no.	Medium	- E_p Values / V vs SOE		
		<i>p</i> -Ochloro-phenacyl bromide	<i>p</i> -Bromo-phenacyl bromide	<i>p</i> -Nitro-phenacyl bromide
1.	Acetate buffer of pH 5.5 in ethanol-water (1:1) mixture	0.08	0.08	0.09
2.	Acetate buffer of pH 6.5 in ethanol-water (1:1) mixture	0.17	0.20	0.12
3.	Ammonium chloride-ammonia buffer of pH 8.2 in ethanol-water (1:1) mixture	0.20	0.21	0.16
4.	0.1 M Lithium perchlorate in ethanol-water (1:1) mixture	0.30	0.34	0.28
5.	0.1 M TEAB in ethanol-water (1:1) mixture	0.34	0.33	0.25

chronopotentiogram for *p*-bromophenacyl bromide obtained in acetate buffer of pH 6.5 in ethanol-water (1:1) mixture is presented in Fig. 3. For *p*-nitrophenacyl bromide in all the media studied, the first peak is found to be proportional to the square-root of scan rate and the i_p vs $v^{1/2}$ plots passes through origin showing the reduction process to be purely diffusion-controlled except in 0.1 M lithium perchlorate in ethanol-water (1:1) mixture, where the i_p vs $v^{1/2}$ plot obtained is linear but

not passing through the origin (Fig. 4). The i_p vs $v^{1/2}$ plots of *p*-bromo- and *p*-chloro-phenacyl bromides are also linear and almost passing through the origin. The weak adsorption of the product may be responsible for the sudden fall of current

Fig. 4. Plots of i_p vs $v^{1/2}$ in (A) acetate buffer, pH 5.5, (B) acetate buffer, pH 6.5, (C) ammonium chloride-ammonia buffer, pH 8.2, (D) 0.1 M LiClO₄, and (E) 0.1 M TEAB (all prepared in 1:1 ethanol-water) for *p*-nitrophenacyl bromide.

TABLE 2—KINETIC PARAMETERS FOR SUBSTITUTED PHENACYL BROMIDES IN ACETATE BUFFER OF pH 6.5 IN ETHANOL-WATER (1 : 1)

Compd.	$\alpha\%$		$\times 10^4 D, \text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$		$\times 10^4 k_{f,h}^0, \text{cm}^{-1}$	
	O.V	O.P	O.V	O.P	O.V	O.P
<i>p</i> -Bromophenacyl bromide	0.558 5	0.809 0	0.465 8	0.885 6	1.505 9	1.778 2
<i>p</i> -Chlorophenacyl bromide	0.592 0	0.889 5	0.152 5	0.300 7	0.946 9	1.977 2
<i>p</i> -Nitrophenacyl bromide	0.493 3	1.100 0	0.111 1	0.090 7	3.689 9	6.054 8

to a very low value in the second sweep in multi-cyclic voltammograms. The ($i \tau^{1/2}$) values obtained from chronopotentiometric data for all the compounds in all the media were found to be almost constant.

Evaluation of number of electrons involved : The reduction peak at more positive potentials for *p*-nitrophenacyl bromide is due to carbon-bromine reduction, and the second peak is due to the reduction of nitro group. The nitro group reduction is a four-electron reduction process. The number of electrons involved in the carbon-bromine bond reduction process in *p*-nitrophenacyl bromide is evaluated by the comparison of $i_p/\nu^{1/2}C$ values of this peak with that of nitro group reduction peak in the same compound. This comparison showed that the first peak involved two-electron reduction process. By comparing the $i_p/\nu^{1/2}C$ values of the first reduction peaks of *p*-nitrophenacyl bromide and *p*-chlorophenacyl bromide, the number of electrons involved in the electrochemical reduction process of carbon-bromine bond in *p*-chlorophenacyl bromide is determined, and this is also found to be two. In a similar manner, the number of electrons involved in the first reduction peak of *p*-bromophenacyl bromide is found to be two.

Mechanism of the electrode process : The reductive cleavage of carbon-bromine bond in all the three substituted phenacyl bromides in different supporting electrolytes studied is found to proceed irreversibly at a hanging mercury drop electrode involving two-electron addition. The nuclear substitution is found to have no noticeable effect on the ease of reduction of the carbon-bromine bond in phenacyl bromides. This may be due to the fact that the carbon-bromine bond is two carbon atoms away from the benzene nucleus and hence the expected mesomeric and/or inductive effect of the nuclear substituents is considerably weakened. The electrochemical reduction of carbon-bromine bond in α -haloketones studied may be represented as

which follows the fission of C-Br bond, and with subsequent rapid acquisition of proton from the solvent. The involvement of one proton in the electrode process under consideration is also supported from the slope of the plot, E_p vs pH.

Kinetic parameters : Since the electrochemical cleavage of carbon-bromine bond is found to be irreversible in all the media studied, the forward rate constants for the reduction process are evaluated. These values are of the same order in all the media. Transfer coefficient values obtained from cyclic voltammetry and chronopotentiometry in acetate buffer of pH 6.5 in ethanol-water (1 : 1) mixture are presented in Table 2. The diffusion coefficient values evaluated from both cyclic voltammetric and chronopotentiometric data are in good agreement.

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